

***Trichomalopsis apanteloctena* (Crawford)**
[Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae]: correct name for the larval parasite of the rice skipper

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Eupteromalus parnarae Gahan is an important larval parasite of rice skipper *Pelopidas mathias* (F.), leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée), leaf beetle *Oulema oryzae* (Kuwayama), and whorl maggot *Hydrellia griseola* (Fallen) in

South and Southeast Asia. It is also a recorded hyperparasite of *Apanteles rificrus* Haliday on *Naranga aenescens* Moore, *A. parnarae* Watanabe and *A. booris* Wilkinson on *Parnara guttata* Bremer & Grey, *A. chilonis* Munakata on *Chilo suppressalis* (Wlk.), *A. plutellae* Kurdjumov on *Plutella xylostella* (L.), *Apanteles* sp. on *Grapholitha molesta* Busck., and *Meteorus* sp. on *Sesamium inferens* (Wlk.). Recent examination, however, indicates that specimens of the three known species of *Trichomalopsis* Crawford [May] 1913, *Eupteromalus*

Kurdjumov [Jul] 1913 became synonymous with *Trichomalopsis* following the rule of priority in zoological nomenclature. In the same manner, *E. parnarae* Gahan and *T. apanteloctena* Crawford were discovered to be one species (ref. Kamijo, K. and E. E. Grisell. 1982. Species of *Trichomalopsis* Crawford [Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae] from Rice Paddy, with descriptions of Two New Species. Kontyu 50 (1): 76-87). Therefore, the correct name for *E. parnarae* Gahan is *Trichomalopsis apanteloctena* (Crawford). □

Effect of some granular insecticides on rice gall midge

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The effectiveness of seven granular insecticides to control rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) was evaluated at Raipur. Quinalphos 5G, phorate 10G, mephosfolan 5G, diazinon 10G, carbaryl + γ -BHC (Sevidol 4G), chlorpyrifos 5G, and carbofuran 3G were applied at 1.0 kg ai/ha during the 1980 wet season. Chemicals were applied 3 times at 20, 40, and 60 days after transplanting (DT) in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Two-three seedlings/hill were planted in 4 × 6-m plots at 20 × 15-cm spacing. Each plot was divided into 4 subplots, and 9 hills/subplot were

Effect of granular insecticides on rice gall midge infestation and rice yield. Raipur, India, 1980 wet season.^a

Treatment	Silvershoots (%)			Yield (t/ha)
	30 DT	50 DT	70 DT	
Phorate	6.8 a	9.2 b	8.5 c	1.6 a
Chlorpyrifos	6.5 a	4.5 a	2.4 a	1.5 ab
Diazinon	4.8 a	11.9 c	12.3 d	1.5 ab
Mephosfolan	3.0 a	9.1 b	5.6 b	1.3 ab
Carbaryl + Lindane	4.8 a	11.2 c	11.2 c	1.0 ab
Carbofuran	5.6 a	9.6 b	10.8 c	0.9 b
Quinalphos	4.6 a	15.8 e	18.6 f	0.9 b
Untreated	4.1 a	14.2 d	16.2 a	0.3 b

^aDT = days after transplanting. Figures with similar letters do not differ significantly.

examined 10 days after each application for damaged tillers and silvershoots. At 30 DT GM incidence was low and uneven; therefore, differences among treatments after the first application were insignificant (see table). GM incidence increased by 40 DT. Percentage of affected tillers was significantly lower for chlorpyrifos than for the control. Other treatments

were similar to the control. Chlorpyrifos also controlled GM best at 60 DT. Mephosfolan, phorate, and carbofuran also reduced damage.

Only the phorate treatment yielded significantly more (1.6 t/ha) than the untreated control (0.3 t/ha) but chlorpyrifos, diazinon, and mephosfolan treatments also yielded slightly more. □

A leaf dipping method for testing insecticide toxicity

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Rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée is a serious rice pest in southwestern Japan. Insecticide toxicity to the larvae was laboratory tested by leaf dipping. Adult moths, which were collected from fields in mid-Oct 1980, oviposited inside a glass jar. They were fed rice seedlings after hatching. Leaf blades of 12- to

LC₅₀ values of insecticides to rice leaffolder larvae using the leaf dipping method.

Insecticide	LC ₅₀ (ppm) at 25°C					
	1st instar		3d instar		5th instar	
	24 h	48 h	24 h	48 h	24 h	47 h
Cartap	1.2	0.70	2.0	1.3	8.2	6.4
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	2.1	1.9	7.8	7.2	31	21
Dimethylvinphos	4.3	3.7	17	15	27	16
Tetrachlorvinphos	11	9.5	26	22	34	21

15-cm-high plants at tillering stage were dipped for 10 s into 100-ml insecticide solutions diluted with methanol, then air-dried for 5 min. The roots were wrapped

in moist paper. Larvae were released on treated rice seedlings in 3 × 20-cm test tubes in a growth chamber kept at 25°C and 16 L. Larval mortality was recorded

24 and 48 h after insect release.

The LC₅₀ values to larvae varied considerably among the test insecticides (see table). Cartap was most toxic at all in-

stars.

LC₅₀ values of 5 replications of dimethylvinphos on 1st-instar larvae ranged from 3.4 to 4.3 ppm at 24 h and 3.1 to

3.7 ppm at 48 h, indicating that leaf dipping method produces stable results and is a simple way of determining insecticide toxicity to rice leaffolder larvae. □

A technique for preparing rice plants for brown planthopper rearing

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Brown planthopper (BPH) colonies have been reared on susceptible TN1 since the host resistance breeding program began at IRRI in the late 1960s. Five TN1 plants are transplanted in 10-cm-high clay pots, 12 cm in diameter, which are put on tables in the open. Six- to eight-week-old plants are placed in cages and adult male and female BPH released on the plants. After 3 days the plants are transferred to other cages where nymphs emerge in about 1 week.

Until 1976 the BPH population was limited to BPH biotype 1, and occasional stray insects that laid eggs on the plants created no problem because they belonged to the same population as was being cultured for screening. However, when BPH biotype 2 became dominant

BPH egg hatchability on rice plants after hot water treatment.

Seedling age	Water temperature (°C)	Nymphs (no./plant) hatched after submergence in hot water			
		Control	20 min	30 min	40 min
6 wk	41	120	40	25	5
	44	110	30	0	0
8 wk	41	122	20	8	2
	44	125	25	0	0

on the IRRI farm in late 1976, the stray BPH biotype 2 adults laid eggs on the plants before they were used for collecting biotype 1 eggs. Nymphs collected from these plants were a mixture of biotypes 1 and 2. We have tried several ways of maintaining pure colonies. Washing the plants with a water jet before egg caging removed stray adults and nymphs, but not the eggs. Because BPH oviposits in the leaf sheaths, we removed the outer leaf sheaths of plants before egg caging. This minimized contamination, but did not eliminate it.

We then evaluated hot water treatments to kill the BPH eggs within the plants. Six- and eight-week-old TN1 plants were caged with BPH adults. After 3 d of egg laying the plants were submerged in hot water (41°C and 44°C) for 20, 30, or 40 min. Control was no-hot-water treatment. After the treatment, plants were put in the insect-free cages to evaluate egg-hatching after 9 d. The 30-minute treatment in 44°C water killed all the eggs (see table), and did not reduce the growth or vigor of rice plants. We are now using this technique. □

Chemical control of thrips in the rice nursery

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Rice thrips *Baliothrips biformis* (Bagnall) severely damage rice nurseries in the Imphal Valley, Manipur, in Jul and Aug. Nymphs and adults suck the sap of leaves, which turn yellowish and curl from the margin to the middle. Resowing often is necessary.

We tested 1 application of 6 commonly available insecticides for thrips control in 12-day-old P33 nurseries in Aug 1982. Carbaryl, endosulfan, chlorpyrifos, malathion, phosalone, and quinalphos were applied at 0.05% concentration in 5-m² plots with 4 replications. Insecticides were applied with a 3-liter compression sprayer. Initial adult and nymph

Efficacy of insecticides on thrips.

Insecticide	Population of thrips ^a							
	Before treatment		1 DAT		3 DAT		7 DAT	
	A	N	A	N	A	N	A	N
Carbaryl	11	105	0 a	0 a	0.5 a	0.3 a	1.5 a	6 a
Endosulfan	19	77	0 a	0 a	0.5 a	0 a	1.5 a	32 a
Chlorpyrifos	24	13	0 a	0 a	0.3 a	0 a	1.3 a	13 a
Malathion	26	143	0.3 a	0 a	2.5 a	4.3 a	6 a	82 c
Phosalone	14	152	0 a	0 a	0.5 a	0 a	0.8 a	4 a
Quinalphos	19	160	0 a	0 a	0.8 a	0 a	0 a	0.3 a
Control	23	85	12	180	14	76	35	63 bc
CD (P = 0.05)	NS	NS	0.62	2.22	0.62	1.68	1.22	2.70

^aA = adults, N = nymphs. DAT = days after treatment. In a column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

populations were recorded separately for each treatment and replication. Thrips population was counted at 1, 3, and 7 d after spraying.

All insecticides caused significant pop-

dation reduction, and by day 3 had reduced populations to a negligible level in all treatments. After 7 d, quinalphos followed by phosalone and carbaryl had best results (see table). □